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1. Introduction

Within the research lines of Spoke 4, one of our main goals is to experiment with the use of virtual (energy-efficient) technologies within defined and representative real-case scenarios. In particular, we aim to experiment with them using different museum and art collection templates to design specific case studies, deriving and applying best practices that can be further adapted and reused in institutions and contexts with similar characteristics. The six templates of museums and art collections identified are described as follows:

- Type A – high-density and innovative museum;
- Type B – natural history and scientific museum;
- Type C – widespread art gallery;
- Type D – sites museums with tangible and intangible heritage and landscapes, among those that have either low or no virtual and digital implementations with a particular focus in southern Italy;
- Type E – historical palaces, labelled as museums, among the most important in the Italian heritage context, including UNESCO sites;
- Type F – demo-ethnic-anthropological museums, including rural culture museums (with less than 20,000 visitors per year), anthropological museums and museums of art and popular traditions.

In this deliverable, we describe the outcomes of the work conducted with the cultural heritage institutions we have contacted that are compliant with Type F, with whom we have established collaborative research projects. In particular, we have identified a set of cultural institutions with which we have set up specific research projects to put into practice existing and ad-hoc tools developed to provide a system to be freely reusable in a similar context by other cultural institutions not necessarily involved in the project.

Some of these projects, referred to as “*core*” *case studies*, have been conducted in collaboration with companies that provide implementation efforts and institutions that offer domain-specific cultural knowledge and citizen engagement. The companies involved were selected through a public call for applications, supported by the project's funds (i.e., cascade calls). These “*core*” *case studies* have also been accompanied by additional *research case studies* aligned with the project templates and goals, which the partners of Spoke 4 have used to experiment with further adoptions of the aforementioned workflow, methodologies and tools within the project's period.

2. "Core" case studies

2.1. TAZEBAO: Open source environment for the digital valorization of museum collections on display, in storage and in archives. Experimentation with three-dimensional exhibition experiences, immersive virtual reality and interactive web

Outline clear goals and objectives

Describe the initial situation

The TAZEBAO project aims at studying and prototyping a framework of digital tools for the documentation, enhancement, sharing, and narration of the heritage of the Turin's University Museum System (SMA), which is intended to be reconfigurable, scalable, reusable, and easily maintainable over time.

From the institutional point of view, the digital framework is intended to support museum curators in hosting and curating data from heterogeneous sources and in different formats in a more collaborative way. This capability focuses both on the need in optimizing information management related to cultural heritage from two different museums and in providing access to "infinite" interfaces that curators can associate with the storytelling.

On the user's side, digital cultural heritage will be accessible through interfaces designed to enable multidimensional research and create personalised and dynamic pathways through contents.

The core case study represented by SMA involves three different types of cultural objects from the Museum of Criminal Anthropology "Cesare Lombroso" (from now 'Lombroso Museum') and from the Museum of Anthropology and Ethnography of Turin University (from now 'MAET'), specifically: the Art Brut collection, the collection of posters with inmates' tattooed bodies, and the Taíno cotton cemí (informally called 'zemi'), hence the project's acronym TAZEBAO (Tattoo-Zemi-Brut Art).

The digitisation of the documentary, historical, and artistic collections selected from the museums involved will unlock new ways to present both tangible and intangible objects and it will also enhance storytelling through digital online experiences and in-person visits.

Lombroso Museum and MAET are housed in the Palazzo degli Istituti Anatomici (Corso Massimo D'Azeglio 52, Torino), which since 2001 has been the seat of the university museum centre dedicated to scientific positivism in Turin between the 19th and 20th centuries.

Lombroso Museum collects evidence mostly related to the research activities and experiments conducted by criminologist Cesare Lombroso (1835-1909) between the second half of the 18th century and the beginning of the 19th century.

Materials on display and in storage include anatomical preparations, drawings, photographs, crime evidence, handcrafts and artistic productions mostly collected in the asylums and prisons.

MAET was officially born in 1926 by the will of the physician and anthropologist Giovanni Marro (1875-1952). Like the Lombroso Museum, the collections are very heterogeneous, and they consist of human remains, mostly collected by Marro during excavation campaigns in Egypt, ethnographic materials from different countries, and artistic productions made by people with mental diseases.

Both museums preserve and exhibit a very rich collection of Art Brut artworks, artistic productions made by inmates or interns in asylums between the 19th and 20th century and collected in the fields of medicine and psychiatry with the aim of studying mental illness and criminal conduct (Merlo, Nenci 2024; Mangiapane 2021).

The artworks are very heterogeneous: drawings and objects such as pipes, paper origami and textiles from Lombroso Museum, and utensils related to the everyday sphere such as razors, forks and knives, ornamental objects made of wood or bone, watercolours and clothing from MAET.

While Lombroso Museum's Art Brut collection is exhibited and opened to the public, MAET Art Brut collection isn't visible because of the museum closure, and it can be accessible only for research activities.

Figure 2.1.1. Art Brut collection from Lombroso Museum.

The collection of posters with inmates tattooed bodies from Lombroso Museum is part of the museum archival fund and it comprises nineteen male portraits - some with the entire body, others partial - made on paper panels (Petruzzo 2016; Cilli, Montaldo 2018; Cilli et al. 2025).

The men depicted are mostly French deserters and Italian convicts, whom Cesare Lombroso encountered in Turin's prisons presumably between the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the following century.

Regarding execution, these portraits present almost always standardised bodies and visages, while little biographical information on the depicted subject is contained within the caption accompanying the poster.

The first posters digitisation project dates to 2006, when an archival description was also carried out using Guarini Archivi software.

Since 2009 digitised posters can be seen only through a monitor located along the museum visit, a solution adopted for conservation reasons.

Figure 2.1.2. Tattoo installation at the Lombroso Museum.

MAET houses a unique cotton reliquary in its collection, enclosing a human skull dating back to the 15th century and originating from the island of Hispaniola (present-day Dominican Republic/Haiti). This is the only surviving pre-Columbian cotton cemí (a representation of an ancestor or spirit) presently known. The object offers a rare glimpse into the complex rituals and belief systems of the Taíno, the Indigenous people of the Greater Antilles on the eve of European contact. The artifact was recovered from a cave west of Santo Domingo and acquired in 1882 by the Italian consul Giovan Battista Cambiaso, who sent it to Italy before 1902. It was later donated, along with a second wooden cemí, to the Museum of Antiquities in Turin in 1928, and subsequently transferred to the MAET (Ostapkowicz, Pennacini 2024). The cotton cemí represents a seated figure approximately 75 cm in height. A portion of a human skull is embedded within the head. While cotton forms the outer surface of the cemí, its internal structure is composed of various materials.

Figure 2.1.3. Taino cotton cemí from MAET.

In 2022, with the support of the national node of E-RIHS (European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science), a team from the University of Turin conducted a series of analyses on the artifact. In October 2022, three multidisciplinary E-RIHS teams belonging to the MOLAB (MOBILE LABORATORY platform of the infrastructure), equipped with advanced technical instruments, collaborated with researchers from the University of Turin to produce a digital reconstruction of the cemí's surface and internal structure using non-invasive techniques. The project also enabled advanced chemical characterization of the surface materials and a thorough assessment of its conservation status. The techniques employed by MOLAB included visible, IRR, and UVL imaging; X-ray tomography combined with 3D laser surface scanning; and external material characterization through FTIR, UV-vis-NIR reflectance and fluorescence, XRF and XR Flow energy, and Raman spectroscopy. The data collected offer new and exciting insights into the materials and manufacturing techniques, which are now available to both specialists and the broader public.

Describe the chosen technologies to be implemented

Regarding the Art Brut collection, the aim is to enhance the Lombroso Museum and MAET collections through a digital narrative system that includes various media and contributions. This system will allow users to create personalised and heuristic paths.

An interactive station will be set up at the Lombroso Museum for 3D exploration of the posters with inmates' tattooed bodies. Visitors will be able to explore individual

tattoos and access additional information on the biographical stories of the people portrayed.

MAET will experiment with removable installations enriched by Virtual Reality tools and informational hotspots. These will allow visitors to explore a 3D digital model of the Taíno cotton cemí, a 15th-century artefact from the Dominican Republic.

The overall project includes a digital repository with user interfaces designed to make research activities and dynamic pathways accessible to all categories of users involved in the museum experience. These pathways will be based on configurable semantic associations that, in the future, could expand the experience into cross-museum and meta-museum dimensions.

The digitization of the cultural objects involved will open the collections to new possibilities for narrating both tangible and intangible objects, integrating a new level of depth through both fully digital online experiences and physical visits to the museums within SMA.

This new dimension will improve accessibility to the informational heritage through multiple and varied consumption modalities suitable for different cognitive skills and physical abilities.

In fact, the digital repository will be complemented by user interfaces designed to make it possible for all categories of users involved in the museum experience to engage in multidimensional research and create dynamic consumption paths, i.e., based on configurable semantic associations that could, in the future, expand the experience into cross-museum and meta-museum dimensions.

Identify specific challenges and opportunities

The experimentation with the Tazebao prototypes has highlighted several challenges. From a technical perspective, the integration of heterogeneous datasets and the management of sensitive information—particularly regarding the Art Brut artworks and the tattooed inmates' posters—required careful consideration of ethical and legal aspects. In addition, the museums' limited human resources sometimes affected the continuity of the workflow. On the other hand, the process opened up opportunities for interdisciplinary collaboration, bringing together museum staff, technologists, and scholars in the co-design of innovative solutions.

Consider the potential effects on the involved stakeholders (e.g., museums, local public bodies)

For museums, the Tazebao prototypes represent a concrete step towards greater accessibility and digital sustainability. The creation of open and reconfigurable infrastructures will allow institutions to expand their audience, reaching both specialised researchers and a broader public. For local public bodies, the project may

represent an opportunity for cultural and territorial promotion, helping to highlight Turin's commitment to innovation in digital heritage. More broadly, the initiative has the potential to strengthen the role of cultural institutions as inclusive spaces, where technology enhances participation and supports dialogue with communities, schools, and civic organisations

Describe knowledge sharing among project participants

Illustrate the training activities for the staff of the winning companies (e.g., seminars, workshops)

The knowledge-sharing process between the partners of the winning companies (No Real Interactive, TP Design, Brixel and IMAGO) and the Turin University's research team has been structured in different activities: seminars and team meetings, including those with the museum staff.

The seminars were organised during different stages of the research and design process, to reflect the project development and promote communication about the CHANGES initiative. All seminars were open to professors, researchers, PhD students, partners of the winning companies, museum staff and students.

The first seminar was held on 2 October 2024 at the Palazzo degli Istituti Anatomici, the centre where museums involved are located, and it focused on the history of the collections involved and, on the prototypes, selected for the pilot case. As regards the history of the collections involved in the project, an important contribution was made by historical and art history experts, including at international level, who were invited to present their research.

This seminar was also the occasion to underline the technological challenges facing and to highlight the winning companies' expertise.

The second seminar was held on 3 April 2025 at the Turin University's Historical Department. Unito research team and winning companies working on the Museo Egizio pilot case were also involved to highlight the preliminary results of the ongoing research activities. The main topics raised during the discussion were: technologies to be implemented, accessibility of contents, legal framework for the (re)use of digital cultural heritage and management of sensitive data, particularly those related to Art Brut artworks' authors and tattooed inmates' posters.

A third seminar was held on 25 June 2025 at the Museo Regionale di Scienze Naturali di Torino and it was dedicated to the presentation of the prototype for accessing the Art Brut online digital collections. The seminar was organised together with members of Spoke 3 affiliated with the Turin University and it took place during the second part

of a day dedicated to digital technologies applied to the cultural heritage of universities.

Team meetings were held both remotely and in person and they involved partners of the winning companies, museum curators and Unito research team. These meetings allowed the research groups to align themselves with the overall objectives of the project and to define internal tasks and objectives for each partner. A first important step involved sharing scientific literature relating to the collections involved, guidelines for digitisation and data in different formats relating to previous research activities. These digitised resources were collected, stored and made available to the winning companies so that they could take a first look at the material available and evaluate its characteristics in relation to their tasks. In parallel, winning companies shared insights about technologies and methodological aspects such as the structure of the central web-based repository and the technical development of the three prototypes.

Considering the historical and artistic context of the collections involved, particularly for the Art Brut artworks and posters featuring tattooed prisoners from Lombroso Museum, the team members also discussed the technological solutions to be adopted regarding the accessibility and privacy of certain content. While for the Art Brut collection the discussion focused on information relating to the authors of the artworks, for the Lombroso Museum's posters collection the debate centred on sensitive data such as the prisoners' names and surnames, their place and date of birth, and details of their criminal convictions as recorded in the archive documents.

Regarding the project dedicated to Digital Cemí, the collaboration and activities between the University team and the partner organization developed along two main trajectories. On one hand, numerous meetings were held to construct the framework of *hyper-storytelling*, understood as the integration of narrative and educational needs related to the scientific content produced by subject-matter experts, with the technical possibilities afforded by the chosen digital solutions. In particular, the decision to employ immersive and interactive dimensions enabled a reconfiguration of the storytelling approach, allowing for a more complex and layered narrative structure compared to traditional linear formats.

The design of the interactive and immersive components was the subject of extensive discussions aimed at optimizing the use of available sources and conceptualizing a narrative and content structure suited to the interface. Conversely, the interface itself was shaped by the historical and cultural characteristics of the object, its biography, the available sources, and the guidelines emerging from the valorisation strategy. This process fostered a deep synergy between programmers, developers, and art directors on one side, and scholars on the other.

In this context, a scientific committee was established, composed of leading experts in Caribbean archaeology and Taíno civilization, to ensure alignment with the objectives of the digital valorisation project. A final meeting, held in July 2025, saw the partner (No Real Interactive) present and discuss the decisions made throughout the creation and development of the digital prototype.

To accompany the experience of the digital twin, a virtual reality installation was conceived and written, retracing its history and provenance. This component emerged from a second phase of collaboration between No Real Interactive and the University team, with the aim of once again harmonizing authorial and technical intentions with scientific content and sources. During this phase, third-year students from the Bachelor's degree program in *Immersive Environments - Digital Communication* at IAAD, Turin (Academic Year 2024/25), were also involved to diversify the technical and creative skill set.

In conclusion, while the University team and the scientific committee had the opportunity to experiment with the transfiguration of scientific content through new multimedia, and especially multimodal languages, the partner and its collaborators conceived, designed, and developed the prototype by shaping it around the historical and cultural features of the artifact, which define its heritage value and inform its valorisation strategies, following a process that reflects its uniqueness.

Explain the exchange of knowledge by the winning companies regarding how the chosen technologies work and how to use them

In parallel with the seminars and workshops described above, a series of dedicated meetings was organised to facilitate the exchange of knowledge between the winning companies, the University research team, and the museum staff. These meetings, conceived as more technical in nature, were aimed at illustrating the functioning of the technologies selected for the project and at ensuring their correct integration into the wider processes of digitisation and cultural heritage valorisation.

During these encounters, the companies presented the operating principles of the adopted digital solutions, providing insights into software environments, interactive interfaces, and data management tools. Demonstrations were conducted to exemplify how specific methodologies, and technological platforms could be applied to the different prototypes under development. The interactive format of the sessions enabled participants to familiarise themselves directly with the tools, while also creating opportunities to raise questions and discuss potential challenges in relation to usability, accessibility, and sustainability of the solutions.

A particularly significant moment in this process was the demonstration of the Digital Cemí prototype, held on 5 September 2025 at the Museo Regionale di Scienze Naturali di Torino (MRSN). On this occasion, No Real Interactive illustrated in detail the

functioning of the prototype, showing step by step how the interactive and immersive components operate. The company provided a live demonstration of the technical workflow, enabling participants to experience the digital solution and to understand its operative logic, software and hardware requirements, and potential applications in a museum setting. This event therefore represented a key opportunity for transferring practical knowledge to museum staff and for testing the usability of the prototype within its intended context of use.

Describe how the guidelines and prototypes identified (in WP3) have been used (or not)

The Interactive Station: The Tattoo prototype

The Interactive Tattoo Station was designed by the partner Brixel. It offers an immersive and technologically advanced experience in exploring the Lombroso Museum's collection of inmates' portraits.

Through a three-dimensional representation, visitors will be able to explore the tattooed bodies of some of the inmates Lombroso encountered and, thanks to an apparatus of captions, learn about the biographical stories of the subject depicted, the meaning of the individual tattoos and the interpretation given by Cesare Lombroso.

Detail the digitalisation processes

The digitisation process began with the digital acquisition of the inmates' portraits, and it was carried out by one of the winning companies' partners, IMAGO.

Twelve full-length portraits were selected from the Lombroso Museum's collection and a large-format high-definition photograph was taken of each one.

Subsequently, a high-resolution copy of the photograph was used by partner Brixel to generate the 3D humanoid model and to work on the individual tattoos. Each tattoo was cut out to extract the alpha channel and processed to be applied as a texture on the 3D geometry.

The team paid particular attention to reproducing the details of the subject's faces, hair and body types, especially where these were already highlighted in the original artwork.

Figure 2.1.4. Example of contoured tattoos from a poster (Brixel).

Illustrate User interface (UI) and user experience (UX) design

From the point of view of interaction, the project envisages a command-mediated interaction and not a direct one as if it were an inanimate object. This choice is since the interaction takes place with a life-sized digital humanoid, and this may raise some critical issues. First it could generate feelings of discomfort in some visitors. This reaction is influenced by psychological factors such as the emotional valence of the human figure, the feeling of invasion of personal space and the *uncanny valley phenomenon* (the uneasiness provoked by artificial entities resembling humans but not quite convincing).

Secondly, a traditional three-dimensional navigation movement such as zoom, pinch and pan can be disorienting, especially when the model is large. In contrast, a command-mediated interaction avoids altering the proportions of the three-dimensional model, preserving a natural and consistent perception.

In addition, special precautions are being developed to handle the nudity of bodies and the need to select tattoos distributed over the entire figure. The interface is designed to ensure immediate interaction and reduce the visitor's cognitive effort.

To ensure accessibility and usability, the interaction areas will be positioned at a height of more than 80 cm, while the controls will be placed to the side. The main information is placed in the top right-hand corner, while for privacy reasons only the initials of the name are shown.

The commands, well organised and limited to the essential elements, will allow for smooth and intuitive navigation. Visitors will be able to manage the position of the

humanoid model, select different subjects, switch between the three-dimensional model and the original panel, and choose the interface language.

Figure 2.1.5. Example installation view (Brixel).

Thanks to modal windows, the visitor will explore different aspects of the collection, including the characteristics of the individual tattoos, the biography of the inmates portrayed and the peculiarities of the panel.

To attract attention and stimulate interaction, the humanoid performs small movements in its state of rest, but it can also assume different predefined positions at the visitor's request, enabling the display and interaction with less visible tattoos, such as those on the back or lower limbs.

Outline hardware setting

From a technical point of view, the installation is based on a responsive Single Page APP, developed with open-source technologies such as Three.js, React and React Three Fiber. Data is managed through a Wordpress CMS database, integrated via REST API. The data structure will be designed for the repository of the Art Brut collection.

The hardware infrastructure consists of two 177 cm high vertical screens positioned inside the Lombroso Museum and two Linux PCs with dedicated graphics card without the need for particularly powerful components, ensuring an energy-saving mode.

The first PC manages the backend, taking care of the database, the cache for offline use, the local network and the domain, as well as driving the interactions on the first screen. The second PC, connected to the backend of the first, is dedicated to

acquiring usage statistics and managing the second screen. The PCs will be connected to each other via a local network.

The pre-Columbian cotton cemí: the Digital Cemí prototype

The pre-Columbian cotton cemí prototype was designed by No Real Interactive for use through the setup of a mobile exhibition corner, transported via an airfreight-compatible hard case and easily assembled by general personnel, thanks to its modular design, ease of installation, and the provided installation manual.

Detail the digitalisation processes

The development of the artefact's digital twin began with the availability of a high-resolution 3D model of the external shell, obtained through a photogrammetric session, along with a set of images derived from a CT scan, representing internal elements (the skull and the internal support structure composed of wood and stone). This earlier digital twin was developed in 2022 as part of the MAETZE research project (MAET Zemis: A New Virtual Life), funded by the Italian node of E-RISH and carried out using technologies provided by the CNR Mobile Laboratories (Montaldo et al., 2023).

Subsequent processing led to the generation of a high-resolution digital 3D object (geometry + texture + shaders), comprising two distinct layers: one hosting the 3D model of the external shell, and the other hosting the 3D models of the internal components, displayed within a semi-transparent, simplified version of the external envelope.

Illustrate User interface (UI) and user experience (UX) design

The UX/UI design of digital experiences was informed by a review of the relevant literature and best practices from similar digital installations with a focus on accessibility for users with motor, sensory, and cognitive disabilities.

For example, the supporting structure for the touchscreen monitor allows for the lower edge of the screen to be positioned at 20 cm above ground level, enabling wheelchair users to position their feet underneath and approach the screen closely. This setup maximizes the interactive area, optimally situated between 70 cm and 140 cm above ground level.

The main interaction mode displays the digital twin of the cemí at the center of the screen, accompanied by a list of interactive icons on the side, linking to general information sections and multimedia-rich detailed sheets.

Through touch and drag gestures, users can explore the 3D model in 360°, including both surface and internal structures (X-RAY mode).

Several hotspots are integrated into the 3D model; when activated, they open informative pop-ups providing specific details about the materials and distinctive features of the cemí.

Figure 2.1.6. Concept design for temporary/removable museum installation (No Real Interactive).

Outline hardware setting and producing multimedia information content

The mobile corner has been designed to allow indoor exhibition in any location worldwide that provides a minimum space of 25 m² and access to an electrical connection (no data connection is required).

The scenographic setting consists of a series of modular panels and walls decorated with naturalistic themes and informational boxes in Italian, English, and Spanish:

- Invitation panel;
- Historical and territorial background panel;
- Three modular self-illuminating walls serving as a backdrop for the display case and/or the totem for interaction with the digital twin.

The touchscreen monitor serves as the primary I/O interface for navigating the digital twin of the artefact. It is equipped with built-in speakers and connected to a mini-PC, which runs the "ZEMI" digital exhibit offline, using the repository described in previous sections.

Offline operation was chosen to ensure the system's independence from data network availability in any exhibition context worldwide.

The digital corner also includes two VR headsets (META Quest 3S or PICO G3), which may be positioned at the entrance, near the totem, or at the exit. These headsets feature an immersive 360° digital animation, freely inspired by known data concerning the taino cotton cemí, its anthropological context, and historical background.

The digital animation itself is the product of an experimental workflow, created using the "state-of-the-art" generative AI technologies to produce panoramic environments, actors, extras, and scenic props. Generative AI was also used to assist in drafting the script and generating the voiceover audio.

The production of both scientific and narrative informational content was overseen by the scientific coordinators and involved:

- Drafting short (TN1 – first-level text) and medium-length (TN2 – second-level text) narrative texts, descriptions for visually impaired users, and alternative TN1 texts tailored to specific audiences (e.g., school groups);
- Researching historical iconographic material;
- Producing video interviews with members of the international scientific committee, with post-production of subtitles in their native languages and the two additional project languages: Italian, Spanish, and English.

The graphic interface displayed on the touchscreen monitor is designed to ensure that passive informational elements are positioned outside the reach of users with motor impairments, while interactive icons are placed within their accessible area.

Texts are presented using a high-legibility font, with a sufficiently large size to ensure readability at distances up to 70 cm. Additionally, a high-contrast layout can be activated if needed.

A second method of accessing the digital Zemi is available via the user's smartphone. By scanning a QR code, users can access a lightweight online version specifically optimized for modern smartphones.

To monitor the usage of the prototype, an analytics system has been developed. This system collects anonymous statistical data on application usage, including the number of touches, the most visited sections, and other user interaction metrics. No login or personal identifiers are required, ensuring full anonymity.

The source code will be published on public repositories under an open-source license, allowing it to be freely downloaded, reused, and adapted for other contexts.

[The central web-based repository: the Art Brut prototype](#)

Detail the digitalisation processes

The digitisation process of the Art Brut collection was carried out by one of the winning companies' partners, IMAGO, and included both high-resolution photographic reproduction and the creation of three-dimensional models of selected objects.

For the generation of 3D models, a total of 21 artworks were selected from Lombroso Museum and MAET. During the acquisition phase, cultural objects were captured using photogrammetry and employing cross-polarisation technique with a Sony A7iv camera and a Sony FE 90 f/2.8 G lens and a SEL-50F18F (fixed focal length, 50mm, F1.8). A total of around 16,800 shots were taken for the photogrammetry.

Next steps included the generation of high poly models which was around 10,000,000 polygons per model and a diffusion map of 8000x8000 pixels. The optimised model ranges from 20,000 to 30,000 polygons per model with the generation of a diffusion map, a Normal Map and an Occlusion map derived from the High Poly model.

Figure 2.17. Side views of 3D models from the Art Brut collection (IMAGO).

Illustrate User interface (UI) and user experience (UX) design

The Art Brut collection presentation interface takes full advantage of the semantic structure defined in the DIR repository, using a REST API system that allows automatically updated digital content to be retrieved. However, to ensure rigorous editorial control, actual synchronisation only takes place upon manual request.

It has been designed to offer an accessible, modular and visually engaging digital experience. Three main viewing modes have been implemented:

- dynamic grid, for a broad, non-hierarchical viewing experience;
- narrative carousel, for immersive, object-centric exploration;
- archival table, for structured access to data and metadata.

Each object is associated with an in-depth information sheet, which collects high-definition images, descriptions and related resources. Users can browse the collection using semantic filters (author, technique, materials, period, place of production, museum of belonging, tags) or through free text search.

Figure 2.18. Example of series of information related to Art Brut collection (TP Design).

An innovative feature is the possibility for both curators and registered users to create narrative paths. These paths are customisable sequences of museum objects, enriched with introductory texts and stylistic customisations, designed to support educational, thematic or poetic experiences.

The interface is fully responsive and designed in accordance with [Web Content Accessibility Guidelines \(WCAG\) 2.1](#) and [AgID guidelines](#). The Matomo system has also

been integrated to collect anonymous usage data, which is useful for continuously monitoring the user experience.

Outline semantic repository and web interface

The design of the semantic repository and web interface dedicated to the Art Brut collection from Lombroso Museum and MAET was developed by partner TP Design. The aim was to build an open, accessible and interoperable information infrastructure capable of supporting a narrative and inclusive digital (re)use of cultural heritage.

The system is based on the open-source platform Wordpress enhanced by a specific custom plugin that allows complex semantic entities (museum objects, collections, museums, resources, itineraries) to be managed as interrelated Custom Post Types. The plugin implements semantic data structures, permission system for different roles (administrator, curator, researcher), and a REST API infrastructure for publishing content to public interfaces.

The reasons behind identifying Wordpress were guided by several reasons, including the compatibility with the existing infrastructure of the University Museum System (SMA), and compliance with regulatory recommendations for public administration. In fact WordPress is officially recommended for use by public administrations in Italy, which made it a natural fit from an institutional standpoint. Choosing a widely supported and endorsed platform ensures greater alignment with national digital strategies and best practices.

One of the key factors in choosing Wordpress is its flexibility in building narrative and editorial interfaces. In fact WordPress is intrinsically designed to manage narrative, visual and experiential content, especially when the project is not limited to the display of objects but aims to build paths, stories and personalised interactions.

Secondly, WordPress benefits from an extensive and well-established development and maintenance ecosystem. This ensures a wide availability of plugins for key areas such as accessibility, security, caching, and translation; comprehensive documentation; easier access to skilled professionals (developers, sysadmins, editors); and regular updates with long-term compatibility, all supported by a global community.

As a possible repository platform, two technologies were considered and then excluded during the design process: Omeka S and ATON.

Omeka S was considered as a potential repository platform but was rejected for a series of technical, operational and design reasons, in particular:

- limited flexibility and customization, due to the fact that it is primarily designed for standard archival viewing and offers a limited set of tools for developing

complex narrative experiences, personalised paths or visually articulated layouts;

- more restricted and less supported ecosystem, due to the limited availability of plugins, poor documentation and a smaller community compared to those of more popular CMSs;
- less extensibility and rigidity in integration with external systems, which makes integration with custom REST APIs and external services such as Matomo, SPID, social login, cloud services, or remote semantic databases more complex;
- limited control over the front-end level, making it difficult to directly act on the interface structure, rendering logic, and integration of external libraries (such as <model-viewer> for 3D models);
- higher customisation costs for advanced solutions.

ATON, recommended in the guidelines for managing 3D/VR environments (Pescarin et al. 2024), was not adopted for the following reasons:

- it is a complex framework designed for WebXR and immersive applications, requiring a demanding deployment process (Node.js and dedicated server configuration);
- the Art Brut interface required a lightweight and accessible solution, compatible with large-scale public web environments.
- Instead, Google's <model-viewer> component was chosen due to its advantages:
 - easy integration with a single line of HTML code;
 - narrative support for AR modes (WebXR, Scene Viewer, Quick Look);
 - Built-in features such as lazy loading, automatic rotation, and interactive annotations;
 - open source, actively maintained by Google, and compatible with all major browsers.

This choice has enabled 3D content to be integrated in an optimised, effective and accessible way, reducing development times and ensuring long-term compatibility.

In addition, the final decision to use WordPress for developing the document repository and the interfaces for specific applications was guided by the fact that the team already had solid experience with WordPress, having worked with it on previous projects. This familiarity made it a practical and efficient choice, reducing the learning curve and allowing development to move forward more smoothly.

The semantic repository (DIR- Digital Item Repository) is designed to serve as the central hub of the entire information system. At its core, it organises various types of content into well-defined entities, all connected through structured taxonomies and relationships. Here's an overview of the main components defined during the design phase:

- Digitised Museum Object, which is the core of the repository. Each object is described through: a text field (description, short description, further details, text for screen readers, list of exhibitions, bibliography, references); taxonomies, which help classify each object by attributes such as Author, Place of Production, Cultural Context, Subject Matter, Technique, and a set of Tags; relationships, which connect the object to various digital resources—such as images, image galleries, 3D models, audio or video content, PDF documents, and even external links—as well as to the museum that holds the object. In terms of privacy, each object includes two Boolean flags: one indicates the presence of sensitive content, which helps flag images or information that might be considered offensive or disturbing, the other marks sensitive data, particularly related to the "Author" taxonomy, restricting access to authorised users only.
- Resource, digital assets—such as images, videos, or 3D models—that are associated with one or more museum objects. They serve to enrich the user's experience and provide visual or multimedia context.
- Collection, a curated group of museum objects characterised by a descriptive text and metadata that explain the theme or focus of the collection, a connection to one or more museums, and an image resource that acts as a visual cover or representation of the collection.
- Museum, which represents the institution that owns or manages the various objects, collections, and paths. It acts as the anchor point for associating cultural content with its real-world context.

Figure 2.1.9. Central repository's structure and flowchart (TP Design).

The repository is hosted on a dedicated server. The software infrastructure is designed for scalability and reuse and the code for the WordPress theme of the Brut Art interface has been released as open source and documented for future use in other museum contexts.

An automatic content-fetching system has been implemented on the Art Brut interface, with a manual synchronization mechanism for actual publication, ensuring editorial control and information integrity. The specific intervention of the team responsible for the interface concerned:

- the design and implementation of the semantic structure of metadata relating to digitised museum artefacts (descriptive, chronological, relational and multimedia fields);
- the management of the integration between digitised objects and related entities (collections, museums, itineraries).

Outline the introduction of the technology to museum staff or other involved stakeholders (e.g., local public bodies, tour guides)

The introduction of the technologies developed within the Tazebao project to the museum staff was conceived as a gradual and integrated process, closely connected to the activities already described (§3.1, 3.2). While many of the meetings and encounters overlapped in terms of timing and participants, their objectives were here specifically oriented towards training on the use and maintenance of the prototypes, the familiarisation of staff with the technological systems implemented, and the

creation of an environment that could support self-guided learning and long-term management of the solutions.

Particularly significant in this process were the demonstrations carried out, where the companies showcased the prototypes in their functional environments. On these occasions, No Real Interactive provided a step-by-step demonstration of the Digital Cemí prototype, showing precisely how the interactive and immersive components work and how they can be managed by museum staff. Similarly, Brixel presented the functionalities of the interactive tattoo station, emphasising both the opportunities for audience engagement and the practical aspects related to system upkeep. In parallel, the development of the semantic repository dedicated to the Art Brut collection was conducted in close collaboration with curators, who were trained to intervene directly on the platform. Staff members were instructed on how to manage and modify records, how to navigate the tree-structured organisation of the repository, and how to use the editorial tools that allow them to add, update, or refine entries autonomously. This training ensured that the museum staff not only understood the technical infrastructure but were also empowered to contribute actively to the ongoing enrichment and maintenance of the digital archive.

Finally, the Tazebao project envisages systematic collection of feedback from museum staff, to be carried out once the installations are fully implemented and integrated into the exhibition contexts. This feedback will be essential both for evaluating the effectiveness of the training activities and for identifying potential areas of improvement in terms of usability, accessibility, and maintenance.

Describe the experimentation session

Evaluate with real users to track of the effectiveness and appropriateness of the proposed solutions

User testing sessions will be conducted in the coming months, and the results will be published in the final project deliverables.

Work is currently underway on drafting a test to evaluate the experience of the "Digital Cemí" prototype. Based on the guidelines provided by WP5 members, which were shared with the company partners, two tools have been identified to assess the user experience in general and user satisfaction: the User Experience Questionnaire Short Form - UEQ-SF (Schrepp, Hinderks, Thomaschewski 2017) and the Net Promoter Score - NPS (Reichheld, 2003).

Identify strengths and weaknesses (possibly using a SWOT analysis)

The experimentation sessions are expected to highlight both the most effective aspects of the prototypes and the areas that require refinement. Among the

anticipated strengths are the high visual impact of 3D reconstructions, the immersive potential of interactive installations, and the flexibility of the semantic repository in supporting personalised narratives. These elements contribute to making the collections more accessible and engaging for non-specialist audiences. On the other hand, possible weaknesses may emerge in relation to technical performance (e.g., responsiveness of interfaces, hardware limitations), the handling of sensitive data, and the need for continuous updates to maintain long-term usability.

Conclusions

The project Tazebao allows for the identification of the expected long-term impacts, distinguishing them based on their effects on the cultural heritage experience and the involved institutions, specifically the MAET and the Lombroso Museum.

In terms of cultural heritage accessibility, the primary impact concerns the increased visibility of the collections involved, with particular focus on those not accessible to the public due to conservation constraints or logistical limitations of exhibition spaces.

Another significant impact is the introduction of alternative methods of heritage engagement, expanding access to a diversified audience and overcoming traditional on-site visit formats.

Furthermore, the project will have a positive impact on the expansion of historical and archival knowledge, providing access to previously unpublished materials that will enrich and deepen the visitor experience. This will lead to the development of new research topics and approaches within academia and greater public awareness of the potential of digital technology to unlock intangible heritage.

Considering impact on museum staff, a fundamental aspect is the enhancement of the technical skills through the acquisition of new knowledge regarding digital technologies applied to the conservation, management, and valorisation of cultural heritage. Through the web-based semantic repository, curators will be able to organise and manage information on cultural heritage more accurately, updating it periodically and varying the links between narrative content.

A relevant impact also pertains to the strengthening of cultural institutions and different stakeholders' network involved in the conservation, enhancement, and dissemination of cultural heritage, aiming to stimulate the sharing of scientific research, innovative digital solutions, and best practices. In fact, the digital framework developed by Tazebao is designed to be adaptable, scalable, reusable, and easily maintainable over time, facilitating the enhanced accessibility and engagement with cultural heritage. It allows for a more dynamic interaction with digital collections,

ensuring the long-term sustainability and broad dissemination of cultural assets to diverse audiences.

3. Research case studies

3.1. Virtual Environments as Open Archives to Explore the Cultural Biographies of Ethnographic Artefacts at the Museo delle Civiltà' - MUCIV (Rome)

Outline clear goals and objectives

This research case on MUCIV deals with a group of artifacts from the American anthropological collection.

In the old permanent museum exhibit (open to the public until early 2025), the objects were displayed in glass boxes with minimal information recorded in nearby text panels. No digital media whatsoever were employed in the exhibit. At present, the exhibition is closed for reorganization, and the new opening, initially planned for November 2025, is now expected to happen around February 2026.

Our research has been carried out thanks to a grant of the Italian node of the European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RIHS.it) and to the funding obtained by the PRIN2022 project "Knowledge of Things: Reassessing the Indigenous American Heritage in Italy (KNOT)", 2022RHCY5P_002, CUP J53D23013510006. The main aim of our research project is to produce and disseminate information on the cultural biographies, or social lives, of the objects. To pursue this aim, archival, stylistic, and iconographic research, as well as non-invasive material analyses (X-ray fluorescence; Reflection mid-FTIR; UV-Vis reflection and emission; Micro-Raman; Digital microscopy; Digital NIR imaging; Hyperspectral imaging; Fluorescence imaging, X-ray tomography) were performed in collaboration with several research centers of the Italian CNR and Departments of the University of Bologna.

Among the aims of our project is the production of the open access online KNOT platform where all the information collected with the abovementioned analyses can be freely shared. A key aspect of the online platform is the use of 3D digital models of the objects that – as part of a virtual museum – will constitute the entry point to the information. Such online platform, that the Museo delle Civiltà will link to its own website, will provide the opportunity to expand the visitors' experience by allowing them to explore the objects in great detail and access relevant information on their function, materiality, and collection history. The online platform will also ensure the dissemination of the information among the general public, including those persons who do not physically visit the museum, indigenous source communities being among

the most important targets of this dissemination form. Students of different grades and scholars will also be among the expected beneficiaries of the platform.

The 3D models and images produced during our research, as well as information gathered for the KNOT online platform, will also be used to enrich the new onsite exhibit, via QR code. On August 8, 2024, Davide Domenici has been formally named as scientific consultant for the new exhibit of the Museo delle Civiltà, a capacity that helped the transfer of information and technology from the research project to the museum.

The materials produced during the above-mentioned projects in collaboration with the European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RIHS.it) will also be used by the MUCIV to enrich their project "Sistema integrato di gestione dati con Intelligenza Artificiale per la conservazione e fruizione di beni culturali" (see below for further information).

An additional aim of the project has been to collaborate with Alessandro Iannucci and Simone Zambruno, from the University of Bologna, to create a "3D vista" storytelling platform where one of the objects from the collection of the Museo delle Civiltà - a musical instrument made with a human femur - was virtually displayed in the exhibit Benedetto XIV e Bologna. Arti e scienze nell'età dei lumi, on display at the Biblioteca Universitaria di Bologna between May 7 to July 27, 2025. As KNOT project members, we provided the 3D model and the texts to be used for the annotation of the digital object.

Describe how the guidelines and prototypes identified (in WP3) have been used (or not)

Each object was digitized using two complementary techniques: (a) photogrammetry and (b) structured light scanning. This combination results in complete and detailed three-dimensional models.

Photogrammetry (a) is based on three-dimensional reconstruction through a series of photographs taken from various angles. Each image covers an overlapping portion of the previous one, allowing the algorithm to detect common points between the images and generate a dense point cloud. This technique contributes to the definition of the texture of the model.

The structured light scanning technique (b) uses the projection of patterns of light onto the surface of the object. The light, as it deforms according to the surface characteristics of the object, is captured and analyzed by software that calculates its shape and size. The iReal3D scanner was used in these acquisitions, which allows a model to be obtained with high geometric accuracy.

Currently, the acquired data are undergoing post-processing. For the photogrammetric images, 3DF Zephyr software was used, which processes the photographs by identifying common points of interest, calculating the position and orientation of each image in three-dimensional space, and generating a point cloud. From this cloud, the final 3D model is created, consisting of a polygon mesh and a detailed texture.

Structured light scans were processed using the scanner's built-in iReal3D software, which generates a point cloud in real time during acquisition and then automatically builds the polygon mesh.

The next optimization phase involves integrating the models derived from the two techniques to achieve a high-quality final representation. This phase is conducted through specific software, such as Instant Meshes for polygon reduction, and Blender for mesh completion and texture refinement. This process reduces the use of resources such as memory and computing power, while maintaining an adequate level of detail and visual quality.

Finally, the optimized models, visually faithful to the original but with reduced geometry, will be exported in the glTF format with textures included.

Online uploading and visualization: The model exports will then be uploaded to the ATON framework, which enables their optimal use in Web3D applications. The open-source ATON framework, (GPL v3 license), based on Node.js and Three.js, is designed to create Web3D/WebXR applications. It is the result of research and development activities carried out in recent years by CNR ISPC. ATON is a scalable, flexible, and modular tool that enables the creation and deployment of "liquid" Web applications that can be consumed on a wide range of devices (from mobile to immersive VR viewers) and requires no installation by end users. It provides innovative and advanced functionality for the Cultural Heritage sector in terms of 3D presentation, interaction models, annotation, immersive fruition and real-time collaboration.

The workflow includes:

1. Upload of individual models to ATON via CNR internal log;
2. Publishing models along with their metadata;
3. Drafting of texts for selected Points of Interest (Pols):
 - a. Pol drafting.
 - b. Retrieval and cloud storage of media associated with each Pol.
4. Pol placement on ATON, with attached media materials.

Data gathered via γ -ray fluorescence; Reflection mid-FTIR; UV-Vis reflection and emission; Micro-Raman; Digital microscopy; Digital NIR imaging; Hyperspectral imaging; Fluorescence imaging, X-ray tomography will be used by the MUCIV to enrich the project "Sistema integrato di gestione dati con Intelligenza Artificiale per la conservazione e fruizione di beni culturali" ("Integrated data management system with Artificial Intelligence for the preservation and use of cultural heritage"), part of the public calls for INIZIATIVE DI CO-CREAZIONE DI SOLUZIONI INNOVATIVE PER LA VALORIZZAZIONE DEL PATRIMONIO CULTURALE. PNRR MIC3 "Turismo e Cultura 4.0". Investimento 1.1 "Strategie e piattaforme digitali per il patrimonio culturale". Sub-investimento 1.1.11 "Piattaforma di co-creazione e crowdsourcing". CUP: F81F21000010006. The project aims at developing an integrated data acquisition and processing system that uses Artificial Intelligence to detect deterioration in cultural heritage preserved in museums and to manage already acquired metadata.

As far as the collaboration with the Biblioteca Universitaria di Bologna for the Benedict XIV exhibition is concerned, the 3D model that we provided - being too heavy for the intended specific use- has been decimated via Blender software, reducing the number of polygons and consequently the weight to 50 percent. The Virtual Tour was made with 3D Vista software, using photos as 'backdrops' on which to go and insert clickable points (hotspots).

Regarding the guidelines identified by the WP3, our project aims at constructing a Informative storytelling, which provides historical and cultural data with digital annotations and 3D visualizations, enriches the experience with descriptions, images and animations. Such strategy is coherent with the solutions adopted by the Digital Cemí Project, implemented at the Museo di Antropologia dell'Università di Torino (also a Type F Museum) as part of the Core Case Study SMA Unito).

As for the types of digital augmentation described by the WP3, we opt for:

- Object annotation: allows the exploration of different versions of a work through advanced technologies such as infrared or X-ray, revealing hidden layers and evolutionary details.
- Data visualization: overlays detailed information about the objects on display, making connections between artefacts, biographies, historical events, and site contexts.

Outline the introduction of the technology to museum staff or other involved stakeholders (e.g., local public bodies, tour guides)

At the moment, the structure of the KNOT platform and the possibility of linking the platform to the museum's website and of using 3D models, imaging, and scientific data

in the permanent exhibition at the Museo delle Civiltà has been presented and discussed during meetings with the museum curators. A collaboration agreement has been signed between the museum and the Department of History and Cultures, University of Bologna. The selection of labels to be enriched with QR Codes leading to annotated 3D models and other information is underway. Further, specific actions will take place in the next months, when the organization of the new exhibit will start its operative phase.

Describe the experimentation session

Since the organization of the MUCIV permanent exhibition is still underway, no experimentation sessions were so far organized.

Conclusions

The collaboration with the Museo delle Civiltà allowed to apply to the concrete context of the new permanent museum display the research products developed during the project carried thanks to the collaboration with the Italian node of the European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RIHS.it) and during the PRIN2022 project "Knowledge of Things: Reassessing the Indigenous American Heritage in Italy (KNOT)". The annotated 3D models that we developed will be linked to the Museum website as well as accessed through QR codes in the actual museum display. The Informative storytelling, which mirrors solutions adopted by the Digital Cemí Project, implemented at the Museo di Antropologia dell'Università di Torino (also a Type F Museum) as part of the Core Case Study SMA Unito and which provides historical and cultural data with digital annotations and 3D visualizations, was selected as the adequate communication strategy to enrich the experience of museum users both in the virtual and physical museum environments of the Museo delle Civiltà.

3.2. ViMMoB - Virtual Museum Movable Book (Panizzi Library) - Mobile Books Digitization and Knowledge Sharing for Cultural Accessibility

Outline clear goals and objectives

The project, promoted by the Centre of Excellence DTC Lazio - Lazio Technological District for Cultural Heritage and Activities (COE DTC LAZIO) in cooperation with University of Rome Tor Vergata, focuses on the collection of mobile books held by the

Panizzi Library in Reggio Emilia. Due to their complex physical and material characteristics, no extensive digitization effort had been implemented until now. The initiative applies advanced 3D and 2D techniques to enable access, preservation, and reusability of these rare and fragile artifacts. Challenges include material fragility, technical complexity of digitization, and the lack of international standards for description and preservation. The project's methodology aims to define replicable models, supported by semantic enrichment and graph databases, to serve as references for similar collections worldwide.

Describe knowledge sharing among project participants

The project was developed collaboratively, integrating training activities into the operational phases. Team members engaged in shared learning via seminars and technical meetings. The digitization provider contributed their expertise throughout, promoting interdisciplinary cooperation.

Describe how the guidelines and prototypes identified (in WP3) have been used (or not)

Digitization followed dual 2D workflows ("with glass" and "without glass") and a 3D pipeline using structured light, laser scanning, and photogrammetry. A specialized web-based database is being developed to manage and display the outputs, supported by a graph database (Neo4j). Augmented Reality was excluded in favor of more efficient, accessible, and stable interaction models such as HMD-based navigation.

A fully web-based platform is being created for exploration and access. The system enables customized workflows for metadata and digital object management, ensuring high adaptability. Integration with existing infrastructure and long-term data preservation was ensured by outsourcing the hosting to a specialized external partner.

Outline the introduction of the technology to museum staff or other involved stakeholders (e.g., local public bodies, tour guides)

Staff focused on metadata quality and user access strategy, supported by third-party infrastructure specialists. Common standards and data protocols were developed to ensure interoperability and content integrity across systems.

Describe the experimentation session

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A dedicated user-testing session was deemed unnecessary due to the integration with an already tested interface. Nevertheless, the project guarantees strong usability, quality control, and accessibility.

In order to identify strengths and weaknesses, we carried out a SWOT Analysis, which revealed the following elements:

- Strengths: high-quality digitization, web integration, replicability;
- Weaknesses: reliance on external infrastructure, limited in-house tech capacity;
- Opportunities: international reference model, public access to rare content;
- Threats: digital obsolescence, infrastructure sustainability.

Conclusions

The research has made it possible to recover the sixteenth-century modes of experiencing Villa d'Este, enabling a virtual reconstruction of its historical lighting environment. Through the digital reconstruction of specific rooms, it will be possible to create virtual exhibition spaces designed to host temporary displays. These will serve both to reconstruct spaces lost due to the dispersal of the Este collections or to structural changes to the Villa over the centuries, and to support exhibitions of any kind, providing innovative curatorial possibilities at significantly lower costs than traditional exhibitions.

The next step of the research will be the implementation of physical tools that allow for the recreation of the original lighting conditions not only through virtual reconstructions, but also in physical reality. To move forward in this direction, it will therefore be necessary to open new avenues of dialogue with lighting designers and manufacturers of lighting systems, inaugurating an unprecedented synergy capable of redefining the museum experience.

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